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Topic: Applied Artificial Intelligence

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Best Practices for Implementing Real-Time Computer Vision Systems

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Summary: Implementing real-time computer vision systems requires more than just a powerful neural network; it demands a highly cohesive architecture where every component operates seamlessly without causing delays. Because practical pipelines rely on interconnected stages (such as video input, data preprocessing, and network communication) a single bottleneck will instantly destroy the real-time capabilities of the entire system. This work offers a practical roadmap to navigate these real-world bottlenecks. Essential optimization strategies for individual tasks are outlined, including the use of high-performance tensor libraries, just-in-time compilation, and model enhancements like quantization. We provide information on how to leverage asynchronous and concurrent processing to maintain overall system responsiveness. Multithreading can be employed to efficiently handle I/O-bound operations, such as video streaming and network requests. Simultaneously, multiprocessing can be utilized to spawn independent sub-processes, achieving true concurrent CPU and GPU execution for computationally expensive neural network tasks. These architectural best practices are showcased through an application performing real-time human action recognition for virtual humans in VR.

Keywords: Real-time processing, machine learning, computer vision, parallel processing

1. Introduction

We expect real-time computer vision systems to see and react instantly, whether that's a self-driving car spotting a pedestrian or a robotic arm identifying a defect on a fast-moving assembly line. However, as any engineer who has deployed these systems knows, getting a model to perform well in a Python notebook is very different from making it run smoothly in the real world. The challenge is no longer just about building the smartest model; it is about building a system that is fast, efficient and reliable. This work is designed to be a brief and practical roadmap for that journey. We move past the theoretical hype to look at the "nuts and bolts" of what it actually takes to build computer vision systems which run in real time.

It is important to keep in mind that a practical computer vision system comprises not only a single neural network. Usually it contains a variety of components, like components for reading the input (e.g. one or multiple video streams), components for preprocessing the content, multiple neural networks which do different tasks (like object detection, pose estimation, tracking) and components for displaying the result or sending it via network (e.g. via REST). The challenge now is that if *only one* of these components is not real-time capable (e.g. because the latency of the REST calls is too high), this will instantly destroy the real-time capability of the *whole* computer vision system.

Despite its practical importance, there are just a few works in the literature focusing specifically on techniques for real-time computer vision systems. In [1] a programming model and architectural design is proposed for real-time machine learning. The work of

[2] provides techniques for low-latency inference of large language models. Finally, the work of [3] gives an overview of model optimization for edge deployment.

Achieving real-time performance for the whole system is usually only possible by optimizing the components itself in various ways (see section 2) in combination with asynchronous processing (see section 3) of multiple components. In section 4, we will briefly describe a system for real-time human action recognition in VR built upon these principles. We will focus on the *Python* language and a system which utilizes both CPU and GPU, as this is the de-facto standard for machine learning applications.

2. General optimization strategies

In this section, we will focus on strategies for optimizing the runtime of individual components via a variety of techniques, both for general processing steps (e.g. the preprocessing of the input images) as well as for neural network inference. As a first step always a profiling should be done in order to identify the computationally expensive operations, naturally the focus should be put on these.

2.1. General processing steps

In the following, we will describe several important techniques for runtime optimization which can be applied individually or in combination.

Loop iterations over large multidimensional arrays are very expensive in Python due to multiple reasons (large overhead of Python interpreter, no loop vectorization or parallelization etc.). Therefore, one

should aim for replacing these loops with a single function call (or a combination of calls) from a high-performance matrix / tensor library like *numexpr*, *NumPy*, *JAX*, *CuPy* or *PyTorch*.

Another way to speed up python code significantly is via *just-in-time compilation* (JIT). Libraries like *Numba*¹ (see Fig. 1), *JAX* and *Taichi Lang*² translate Python code into optimized machine code using compiler frameworks like LLVM or XLA. This process bypasses the Python interpreter overhead and enables optimizations such as SIMD vectorization and parallelization on CPUs as well as GPUs.

```
@numba.jit(nopython=True)
def gaussian(x):
    return np.exp(-0.5 * x**2) / np.sqrt(2 * np.pi)

@numba.jit(nopython=True)
def numba_kde(eval_points, samples, bandwidths):
    result = np.zeros_like(eval_points)

    for i, eval_x in enumerate(eval_points):
        for sample, bandwidth in zip(samples, bandwidths):
            result[i] += gaussian((eval_x - sample) / bandwidth) / bandwidth
        result[i] /= len(samples)

    return result
```

Fig. 1. Example implementation of 1D Gaussian Kernel estimator in Numba.

Porting runtime-critical routines to a compiled language and invoking them via a Python wrapper can also bring significant speedups, often by an order of magnitude. The *C/C++* programming language is usually employed for that in combination with a Python wrapper library like *pybind11*³ or *nanobind*. The Rust programming language is also a good alternative in combination with the Python wrapper libraries *PyO3*⁴, *rust-numpy* and *maturin*.

```
py::class_<Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps>(m, "ImageProps")
    .def(py::init<>())
    .def(py::init(std::string>())
    .def("getPropString", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::getPropString)
    .def("setFromPropString", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::setFromPropString)
    .def_readwrite("width", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::width)
    .def_readwrite("height", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::height)
    .def_readwrite("nchannels", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::nchannels)
    .def_readwrite("depth", &Jrs::Cuda::ImageProps::depth)
```

Fig. 2. Python wrapper for a C++ class with the *pybind11* wrapper library.

Finally, there are often faster alternatives available for popular Python libraries with an identical or similar interface. For example for handling dataframes, high-performance libraries like *Polars*⁵, *cuDF*, *Modin* and *Dask* can be employed instead of *Pandas*. Similarly, for web requests the libraries *niquests* and *htpx* are often significantly faster than the *requests* library.

2.1. Neural network inference

A range of well-established optimization techniques are commonly used to reduce the cost of neural network inference. One widely adopted

approach is *model distillation*, where a smaller *student network* is trained to mimic the behavior of a larger, more complex *teacher model*. Another key technique is *quantization*, which lowers both memory usage and inference latency by representing 32-bit floating-point weights with lower-precision formats such as 16-bit, 8-bit or even 4-bit integers.

The performance can be further improved by taking advantage of highly optimized GPU inference frameworks like *NVIDIA TensorRT*⁶ or specialized frameworks for large language models and vision-language models such as *vLLM*⁷, *lmdeploy* and *SGLang*. Many neural network architectures also offer multiple backbone variants of varying complexity and support different input resolutions. For example, the very popular *Swin Transformer* backbone supports a variable input resolution and comes in four different variants: *tiny*, *small*, *base* and *large*. Selecting the smallest input resolution and backbone variant that still gives the desired quality for the task can give a significant speedup for the inference.

3. Asynchronous / concurrent processing

Asynchronous and concurrent processing allows an application to process multiple of its components in parallel, instead of executing everything one step after another. This is crucial for the real-time capability of a computer vision system, especially when it has to deal with slow I/O operations or computationally expensive tasks. In Python, this is usually handled in two main ways: *multithreading*⁸ and *multiprocessing*⁹. In the following, we will describe both concepts briefly.

3.1. Multithreading

In Python, multithreading allows a program to handle multiple tasks concurrently in a single process by switching between different threads of execution, using constructs like *Thread* and *asyncio*. It is important to keep in mind that multi-threading in Python cannot be regarded as true parallelism for computationally expensive tasks because the *Global Interpreter Lock* (GIL) demands that only one thread executes Python bytecode at a time, effectively serializing execution.

Furthermore, multiple concurrent GPU inference calls with PyTorch usually leads to *implicit serialization*, as all threads likely employ the *same* (default) *CUDA stream* for GPU kernel execution, effectively queuing operations on the GPU instead of running them in parallel. Consequently, multithreading is *best suited for I/O-bound operations*, such as streaming video input or sending results via a REST API, where the component would otherwise sit idle waiting for data to receive or send out.

¹ <https://numba.pydata.org/>

² <https://www.taichi-lang.org/>

³ <https://github.com/pybind/pybind11>

⁴ <https://github.com/pyo3/pyo3>

⁵ <https://github.com/pola-rs/polars>

⁶ <https://tensorrt.org/>

⁷ <https://github.com/vllm-project/vllm>

⁸ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/threading.html>

⁹ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/multiprocessing.html>

3.2. Multiprocessing

Unlike multithreading, which as mentioned is constrained by the Global Interpreter Lock (GIL), the approach via *multiprocessing* involves spawning independent sub-processes, each equipped with its own dedicated Python interpreter and memory space. This decoupling ensures that multiple components can execute *truly concurrently* for both CPU and GPU operations. On the other hand, the creation (spawning) of a new sub-process is a heavyweight operation, resulting in non-trivial startup latency compared to the creation of a thread. Furthermore, since processes do not share a common address space, inter-process communication (IPC) is needed in combination with serialization of Python objects via *pickling*. Especially for large objects like images, this can induce significant overhead.

4. Real-time human action recognition

A computer vision system implemented according to these guidelines is presented in [4][5]. The *Visual Analyzer* Python application is able to detect multiple actions performed by virtual humans in VR in real time.

The application does the processing of the input video stream (generated by Unity) in multiple steps. First, all virtual humans are detected with a deep learning based object detector (*Yolo-V4*) and tracked with an optical flow based method. In parallel, for all detected humans their 2D pose (skeleton) is calculated with a deep learning based pose estimation algorithm (*RTMpose*). The actions of all virtual humans are now calculated with a deep learning based action recognition algorithm (*PoseConv3D*) from the trajectory of its 2D poses within an analysis period of roughly two seconds. All detected actions are then sent back via REST API to the PC where Unity runs. Initial experiments on several XR Unity scenes recordings with different types of virtual humans demonstrate that their actions can be detected robustly, as can be seen in Figure 3.

The application has been optimized heavily with the methods presented in this work, in order to make it real-time capable. Multiprocessing is employed for the AI components which are responsible for object detection and tracking, pose estimation and action classification. In contrast, multithreading is used for video I/O and sending the result back to Unity via REST API. The neural network inference for the pose estimation step has been ported from PyTorch to TensorRT, which makes it four times faster.

Fig. 3. Illustration of successfully detected actions for different kinds of virtual humans.

With all these optimizations, the application is able to detect human actions in real-time for up to five humans in the scene, with a latency of roughly two seconds.

Conclusion

We described a variety of practical methods for achieving real-time performance for computer vision systems, ranging from general optimization strategies to asynchronous / concurrent processing and applied these methods successfully to an application for real-time human action recognition.

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant No. 101135025, "Presence XR".

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